

Commercial Advertisement and the Freedom of Speech & Expressions

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Abstract

Article 19(1)(a) of the Constitution of India guarantees freedom of speech and expression. Right to advertise is not the distinct right under Part III of the Constitution but it is included under the right of freedom of speech and expression and thus can be regulated by the Executive on grounds of reasonable restrictions under Clause (2) of Ar. 19 of the Constitution. Moreover it has also to satisfy the requirement of law related to obscenity and other regulatory mechanism.

Keywords: Freedom of Speech and expression, commercial speech, advertisement.

INTRODUCTION

In a largely capitalistic economy, advertisements are one of the most important sources of creating awareness about various products. Companies continue to employ the most innovative techniques to woo their customers and boost sales. The essence of free speech is the ability to think and speak freely and to obtain information from others through publications and public discourse without fear of retribution, restriction or repression by the Government. Advertising is a form of communication for marketing. Hence commercial advertisement cannot be denied the protection of Ar. 19(1)(a) of the constitution.

Six fundamental freedoms have been guaranteed by Ar. 19(1) of the Constitution. Freedom of speech and expression is one of them. These six freedoms are however, not absolute. Absolute individual rights cannot be guaranteed by any modern state. As Patanjali Shastri, j., in A.K. Gopalan's case observed:

"Man as a rational being desires to do many things, but in a civil society his desires have to be controlled, regulated and reconciled with the exercise of similar desires by other individuals."

The guarantee of these six freedoms is, therefore, restricted by the constitution itself by conferring upon the state a power to impose by law reasonable restrictions as may be necessary in the larger interest of the community.

FREEDOM OF SPEECH AND EXPRESSION

Freedom of speech and expression means the right to express one's own convictions and opinions freely by words of mouth, writing, printing, pictures or any other mode. It thus includes the expression of one's ideas through any communicable medium or visible representation, such as, gesture, signs and the like. Freedom of speech and expression is indispensable in the society. In Romesh Thapper v. State of Madras, Patanjali Shastri, J., rightly observed that:

"Freedom of speech and the press lay at the foundation of all democratic rights, for without free political discussion no public education, so essential for the proper functioning of the process of popular Government, is possible. A freedom of such amplitude might involve risks that have been well reflected by Madison, who was the leading spirit in the preparation of the First Amendment of the Federal Constitution, that it is better to leave a few of its noxious branches to their luxuriant growth than by pruning them away, to injure the vigour of those yielding the proper fruits."

CONTROL MECHANISM

Right to freedom of speech and expression which includes right to advertise like other fundamental freedoms guaranteed by Article 19 is not absolute. Absolute individual rights cannot be guaranteed by any modern State. There cannot be any right which is injurious to the community as a whole. If people were given complete and absolute liberty without any social control the result would be ruined. The restriction which may be imposed

under any of the clauses of Article 19 must be reasonable restriction. But these restrictions cannot be arbitrary. A restriction to be constitutionally cannot be arbitrary. A restriction to be constitutionally valid must satisfy the following two tests –

- (1) The restriction must be for the purposes mentioned in clauses 2 to 6 of Article 19.
- (2) The restriction must be reasonable restriction.

Thus the restriction on the right to freedom of speech and expression which includes the right to advertise can only be imposed by a law and not executive or departmental instructions. The word reasonable implies intelligent care and deliberation which reason dictates. A law which arbitrarily or excessively invades the right of a person cannot be said to contain the quality of reasonableness and unless it strikes a proper balance between the right guaranteed in Article 19(1) and the social control in Article 19(2) – (6), it must be held to be wanting in that quality.

The word ‘reasonable’ thus widens the scope of judicial review and the determination by the legislature as to what constitute as reasonable restriction is not final and conclusive but subject to the supervision of the Supreme Court.

Clause (2) of Article 19 contains the grounds on which restrictions on the freedom of speech and expression can be imposed. It provides that –

“Nothing in Sub-clause (a) of Clause (1) shall affect the operation of any existing law, or prevent the State from making any law, in so far as such law imposes, reasonable restrictions on the exercise of the right conferred by the said sub-clause in the interests of the sovereignty and integrity of India, the security of the State, friendly relations with foreign States, public order, decency or morality, or in relation to contempt of Court, defamation or incitement to an offence.”

We shall now discuss the above mentioned grounds of restriction on freedom of speech and expression briefly.

- (a) **Sovereignty and Integrity of India** – This ground was added to clause (2) of Article 19 by the Constitution (Sixteenth Amendment) Act, 1963. Under this clause, freedom of speech and expression can be restricted so as not to permit to anyone to challenge the integrity or sovereignty of India or to preach cession of any part of India from the Union.
- (b) **Security of the State** – Reasonable restrictions can be imposed on freedom of speech and expression in the interest of security of the State. The words “in the interest” of before the words “Security of the State” clearly imply that the actual result of the act is immaterial. An incitement to an armed resolution, though infructuous, ultimately is enough to attract the term “security of the State”.
- (c) **Friendly relation with Foreign States** – This ground was added by the Constitution (1st Amendment) Act, 1951. The object behind the provision is to prohibit unrestrained malicious propaganda against a foreign friendly State which may jeopardize the maintenance of good relations between India and the State.
- (d) **Public Order** – This ground was added by the Constitution (First Amendment) Act, 1951, in order to meet the situation arising from the judgment of the Supreme Court in Ramesh Thappar’s case. It was held by the Court in that case that ordinary or local breaches of public order were no grounds for imposing restriction on the freedom of speech and expression guaranteed by the Constitution.
- (e) **Decency or Morality** – The words “morality or decency” are words of wide meaning. The word ‘obscenity’ of English law is identical with the word ‘indecent’ under the Indian Constitution. The test of obscenity is whether the tendency of matter charged as obscene is to deprave and corrupt those whose minds are open to such immoral influences and into whose hands a publication of this sort is likely to fall. Thus an advertisement is obscene if it tends to produce lascivious thoughts and arouses lustful desire in the minds of substantial number of that public into whose hands the advertisement is likely to fall.
- (f) **Contempt of Court** – Restriction on the freedom of speech and expression can be imposed if it exceeds the reasonable and fair limit and amounts to Contempt of Court. According to Section 2 of the Contempt of Court Act, 1971, Contempt of Court may be either civil contempt or criminal contempt.
- (g) **Defamation** – A statement which injures a man’s reputation amounts to defamation. Defamation consists in exposing a man to hatred, ridicule or contempt. Section 499 IPC contains the criminal law relating to defamation.
- (h) **Incitement to an Offence** – This ground was also added by the Constitution (First Amendment) Act, 1951, Freedom of speech and expression cannot confer a license to incite people to commit offence.

RIGHT TO ADVERTISEMENT AS A PART OF FREEDOM OF SPEECH AND EXPRESSION:

So far as advertisement is concerned there is no doubt that an advertisement is also a form of speech. But every form of advertisement is not a form of speech or expression of ideas. Advertisement when it takes the form of commercial advertisement no longer falls within the concept of freedom of speech for the object of such advertisement is not the propagation of ideas-social, political or economic or furtherance of literature or human thought. Thus an advertisement of commercial nature is not protected under Art. 19(1) (a) of the constitution such ads have only an element of trade and commerce.

In **Hamdard Dawakhana v. Union of India** (AIR 1960 SC 554) the validity of the Drug and Magic Remedies (Objectionable Advertisements) Act, 1954 which puts restrictions on advertisement of drugs in certain cases and prohibited advertisement of drugs having magic qualities for curing diseases was challenged on the ground that the restriction on the advertisement abridged the freedom of speech. The Supreme Court held that an advertisement is no doubt a form of speech but every advertisement is not a matter dealing with the freedom of speech and expression of ideas. In the present case the advertisement was held to be dealing with trade or commerce and not for propagating ideas. Advertisement of prohibited drugs would thus not fall within the scope of Art. 19(1)(a) of the constitution.

Thus, a law which puts restrictions on the publication, through the medium of press or other means, of advertisement to promote the sale of certain goods does not violate the right to free speech or the press. Here the advertisement is a part of business, it has the object or furthering business and has no relationship with the concept of freedom of speech which is a privilege of propagation of ideas or furtherance of literary or humane thought. A commercial advertisement does not aim at the furtherance of the freedom of speech.

In **John W. Rast V. Van Deman and Lewis Company**, Mr. Justice Mckenna, dealing with advertisements said - Advertising is a merely identification and description, apprising of quality and place. It has no other object than to draw attention to the article to be sold and the acquisition of the article to be sold constitutes the only inducement to its purchase.

Right to advertisement is one of the intrinsic features of conducting any business, profession, or any other organization in today's world. A person can transmit every type of information to the general public, provided that such advertisement conforms to the norms and regulations established in this regard.

In **Indian Express Newspaper Vs. Union of India** (1985 1SCC 641), Supreme Court held that commercial speech is protected under the ambit of free speech and expression under Ar. 19. Court said that, "we are of the view that all commercial advertisement cannot be denied the protection of Ar. 19(1)(a) of the Constitution merely because they are issued by businessman and its true character is detected by the object for the promotion of which it is issued."

In Tata Press Ltd. V. Mahanagar Telephone Nigam Ltd. (1995 5 SCC 139).

The Mahanagar Telephone Nigam is a government company controlled by the Government of India. The Nigam is a licensee under the Act and as such is required to establish, maintain and control the telecommunication service within the territorial jurisdiction of the Union Territory of Delhi and the Municipal Corporations of Bombay, New Bombay and Thane. Till 1987 Nigam used to publish and distribute the telephone directory itself consisting of white paper only. However, from 1987 the Nigam started to entrust the publication of its telephone directory to outside contractors. The Nigam permitted such contractors to raise revenue for themselves, by procuring advertisements and publishing the same as yellow pages appended to the telephone directory. Thus, the telephone directory published and distributed by the Nigam consisted of the "white pages" which contain list of telephone subscribers and also "yellow pages" consisting of advertisements procured by the contractor to meet the expenses incurred by the contractor in printing, publishing and distributing the directory. Tata Press Ltd. were engaged in publication of the "Tata Press Yellow Pages". The Nigam and the Union of India filed a civil suit before the Civil Court at Bombay for a declaration that they alone have the right to print or publish the list of telephone subscribers and Tata Press Ltd. had no right to print or publish without its permission as it was violative of the Indian Telegraph Act and they should, therefore, be restrained by permanent injunction from publishing the 'yellow pages'. The City Civil Court dismissed the suit. But a single judge of the Bombay High Court allowed the appeal. Tata's Letters Patent Appeal was dismissed by the division Bench of the High Court. They filed an appeal in the Supreme Court. It was held that commercial speech (advertisement) is a part of the freedom of speech and expression granted under Article 19(1)(a) of the Constitution. It can only be restricted on

the grounds specified in Clause (2) of Article 19. The Court, however, made it clear that the commercial advertisements which are deceptive, unfair, misleading and untruthful could be regulated by the Government.

The advertisement as a commercial transaction has two facets. Advertising which is no more than a commercial transaction, is nonetheless dissemination of information regarding the product advertised. Public at large is benefited by the information made available through the advertisements. In a democratic economy, free flow of commercial information is indispensable. The economic system in a democracy would be handicapped without there being freedom of "Commercial Speech", Article 19(1)(a) of the Constitution not only guaranteed freedom of speech and expression, it also protects the rights of an individual to listen, read and receive the said speech.

But misleading, deceptive and obscene advertisements would not fall within the protection of Ar. 19. A misleading advertisement is one that deceives, manipulates or is likely to deceive or manipulate the consumer. The courts have tried to strike a balance between protecting the rights to commercial speech and the interest of consumers and competitors.

In **Dabur India V. Colortek Meghalaya Pvt. Ltd.**, 2010 SCC Online 802 Delhi High Court laid down the following guiding principles while dealing with the issue of misleading advertisements.

1. The Advertisement are protected under Ar. 19(1)(a) as commercial speech.
2. An Advertisement must not be false, misleading or deceptive.
3. However, there are certain cases where the advertisement must not be taken as false but as a glorious representation of one's own product and only when the impugned advertisement goes beyond glorifying its product and is deceptive & misleading, the protection under Ar. 19(1)(a) would not be available.

In **Havells India Ltd. V. Amritanshu Khaitan**, 2015 5 SCC Online Delhi 8115 the Delhi High Court observed that comparative advertising is healthy & encouraged in the spirit of competition, disparagement is not and a cause of action shall arise in case of misleading advertisement.

Since advertising is a very powerful and rich medium. So every businessman must have right to advertise its product. But at the same time no civilized society will permit negative liberty to its members. That's why various restrictions have been imposed by numerous enacted laws, for instance, the Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986 and laws relating to obscenity which are provided under sections 292-294 of the Indian Penal Code are some of the legislations to regulate this right.

Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986 prohibits Indecent representation of women through advertisement or in publications, writings, paintings, figures or in any other manner or for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto. To give effect to the International Convention for the Suppression of the Circulation of and Traffic in Obscene Publications which was signed in Geneva in 1923, the I.P.C. incorporated Sections 292 and 293. The Penal Code was silent on the definition of word obscenity in the beginning but with a view to make the existing law more definite, more clear the provisions were amended by Act XXXVI of 1969. Now clause (1) of Sec. 292 explains the expression obscenity in the same terms as in the Hicklin's rule.

CONCLUSION

In a democratic economy free flow of commercial information is indispensable. But that free flow of information cannot & should not be allowed without any control. Ours is a welfare state, hence it is the responsibility of each government to exercise strict control over this right and the need of the hour is that the Advertising Code of Conduct be given a legal shape and provisions for prosecution and punishment should be included therein.

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